

	AGAP010735	Sal_Perox	Sal_Perox2	Perox3	Perox4	Perox5
AGAP010735	100	54.44	75.55	54.03	53.74	49.15
anoalb_Sal_Perox	54.44	100	53.68	50.6	72.33	47.46
anoalb_Sal_Perox2	75.55	53.68	100	52.92	52.81	51.61
anoalb_Perox3	54.03	50.6	52.92	100	48.89	45.72
anoalb_Perox4	53.74	72.33	52.81	48.89	100	47.8
anoalb_Perox5	49.15	47.46	51.61	45.72	47.8	100